

DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL FITNESS OF JUDOKA GIRLS USING SPECIAL EXERCISES

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Annotation. This in the article special from exercises used without free of wrestlers technical and physical readiness development efficiency cause.

Keywords: special exercises, free wrestlers, technique, physical preparation, efficiency.

Actuality. It is a free sport that is practiced year after year on a global scale the number of wrestlers is increasing. In the world, a large number of scientific studies have been conducted in the field of training of wrestlers, in particular, on the development of their quick-power training, technical-tactical skills, functional training, strength and power qualities. Scientific research in the theory and methodology of freestyle wrestling has been carried out on wrestlers of different ages and qualifications, according to various criteria of preparation. In particular, in the parterre, there are scientific-research works related to improving the methodology of training athletes based on the priority implementation of attack methods, standardization of training loads based on individual characteristics, and increasing technical-tactical and physical fitness. In recent years, freestyle wrestling has become the most popular sport, but in the stage of sports improvement, there is not enough research aimed at studying the issues of optimization of training tools with the introduction of competitive loads into the training process, taking into account the number of competitions and their duration.

In the present period, the training process in international research institutes, leading scientific research centers in higher education institutions on the problems of

improving the physical, functional, technical-tactical, psychological training of athletes in sports wrestling, building endurance, adaptive physical education and sports development. Although promising researches and researches based on many modern instrumental methods are being carried out regarding the necessary issues of complex control, quick management of training loads in sports, they are not enough for today's requirements.

The purpose of the study. It consists in developing the effectiveness of developing technical and physical fitness of freestyle wrestlers using special exercises.

Research methods and organization: analysis of scientific and methodical literature, questionnaire, pedagogical observation, pedagogical testing, pulsometry, instrumental method, pedagogical experience and mathematical statistical methods.

Research results and them discussion do:

Techniques of wrestling are based on methods (application of methods) - these are goal-oriented offensive actions, with the help of which the wrestler gains an advantage over his opponent. Each method consists of two parts. The first part is to capture the method. Grabs are divided into grabs from the top, bottom, back, front, side, etc. The catch is very important in the successful execution of the method. The quality of performance of all methods depends on how well the capture is done.

Scientific aimed at developing physical qualities of wrestlers analysis of research shows that recently in the field of sports the attention of specialists is the most effective means of physical training and aimed at choosing and learning styles. Such tools and methods are student sportsman organism functional to systems high requirements puts of these systems opportunity exactly competition of activity success set gives

In order to achieve the goal set by the coach, he must clearly plan the means and methods of solving the tasks.

In order to determine the physical fitness of the freestyle wrestlers, the physical fitness indicators of the experimental and control group wrestlers were analyzed and were as follows.

10 times (seconds) Jumping back and forth with the opponent's left hand holding the sleeve, hanging on the right leg and leaning on the left leg was 8.31 ± 1.15 seconds in the experimental group, while in the control group this indicator was 7.92 ± 1.21 seconds.

10 times (seconds) Holding the elbow of the opponent with the right leg, first pulling the left leg, then the right leg was 9.98 ± 1.31 seconds in the experimental group, and 9 ± 1.12 seconds in the control group.

10 times (seconds) Holding the opponent's left shoulder with the left hand, holding the elbow and hanging with the leg was 27.02 ± 2.95 seconds in the experimental group, and 26.78 ± 3.39 seconds in the control group.

10 times (seconds) Pushing the opponent's hand on the elbow with the right foot on the opponent's left ankle and the left foot on the back of the right ankle in the experimental group was 16.69 ± 1 seconds, while it was 17.05 ± 2.02 seconds in the control group.

10 times (seconds) Holding the opponent's elbow and pulling the right and left foot on the inside and outside of the opponent's left ankle was 12.01 ± 1.73 seconds in the experimental group, and 11.88 ± 1.92 seconds in the control group.

In order to achieve the intended goal during the research, a comparative analysis of the results of the free wrestlers at the end of the experiment was given.

10 times (seconds) Jumping back and forth with the opponent's left hand holding the opponent's sleeve, the right leg hanging on the opponent's right leg and leaning on the left leg was 7.06 ± 1.01 seconds in the experimental group, while in the control group this indicator was 7.88 ± 1.11 seconds. The difference is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

10 times (seconds) Holding the elbow of the opponent with the right leg, first pulling the left leg, then the right leg was 8.61 ± 1.11 seconds in the experimental group, and 9 ± 1.22 seconds in the control group. The difference is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

10 times (seconds) Holding the opponent's left shoulder with the left hand, holding the elbow and hanging with the leg was 23.63 ± 2.91 seconds in the

experimental group, while in the control group it was 25.95 ± 2.97 made a second. The difference is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

10 times (seconds) with the opponent's hand on the elbow with the right foot on the opponent's left ankle and with the left foot on the back of the right ankle in the experimental group $15.13 \pm 1.1.83$ seconds, while in the control group it was 16.65 ± 1.92 seconds. The difference is statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

10 times (seconds) Holding the opponent's elbow and pulling the opponent's right and left foot on the inside and outside of the opponent's left ankle was 10.81 ± 1.21 seconds in the experimental group, was 11.14 ± 1.42 seconds in the control group. The difference is statistically unreliable ($P > 0.05$).

At the end of the study, the analysis of the dynamics of the physical fitness indicators of the experimental group wrestlers shows that the indicators of the experimental group wrestlers are significantly superior to those of the control group, and the level of reliability is found to be high.

During the training of free-style wrestlers in sports wrestling, various loads used in the training stages of qualified wrestlers were systematized as one of the available factors of increasing the level of UJT and MJT of wrestlers. Including, in the training of qualified athletes in wrestling, physical abilities of athletes and sports in microcycles based on the program of the selected direction in practice, based on the indicators obtained as a result of the organization of training in a rational order, according to the size of the loads and the direction during the experiment the importance of the opportunities that ensure the serious growth of the results was shown.

conclusion, we can say that the practice of modern wrestling has moved from a combinatorial understanding of the fighting style to a situational style, which is based on confidence, the ability to use the strength of the opponent, self-reliance and flexibility, based on the physical ability to perform any technical movement necessary at the moment (development of readiness) requires complex preparation. In the course of the research, the increase in physical fitness indicators of free wrestlers was evaluated based on subjective registration. At the end of the ban, a high level of

statistical reliability was observed in comparison to the changes in the arithmetic mean of the control group.

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